

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

CHALLENGES OF THE COUNTRY'S SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITION AGAINST THE BACKDROP OF MIGRATION PROCESSES

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Abstract

Migration processes are quite diverse both in terms of causes, as well as in their form and results. The assessment of its impact on both sides ("giving" and receiving countries) is related to a number of socio-economic issues. Moreover, in most cases of intensive and large-scale migrations, political signs are also in excess. Migration in different regions of today's world is characterized by different specific features. Accordingly, the assessment of its results and impacts is also different. The economic crises of the 21st century, the Covid-19 pandemic, and the hostilities in various regions in recent years have had a significant impact on both the employment of the workforce and the provision of living conditions and social protection for refugees. Due to the current situation, migration processes have become an important and popular topic of research and analysis. The assessment of its consequences (both positive and negative) is complicated by the diversity and peculiarities of the processes, which are directly related to the causes of the origin. That is why it is not easy to talk about the results. Mass migration of people leads to significant changes in a number of demographic processes, which are sharply reflected in the gender and age structure of the population. Changes in indicators are visible in the dynamics of birth and death rates, the number of jobs and living standards, the outflow of skilled labor, and the aging of the population.

Keywords: Labor migrants, unemployment, "brain drain", silver economy, reintegration.

In today's world, the migration process is one of the most important events, which is quite diverse in terms of its causes and consequences. In recent years, its scale has grown so much that it often poses a serious problem to those countries to which immigrants flock en masse.

Historically, migration processes have been known to Georgia since ancient times. There were frequent cases of massive influxes of people of other nationalities, most of whom remained as permanent residents (Greeks, Jews, Russians...). In recent history, as a result of events and processes developing in the country, the population of Georgia began to leave the country in the form of labor migration. Initially, the process started in the 90s of the 20th century. It resulted from the problems accompanying the transition to a new economic system (unemployment, worsening of social conditions). A difficult socio-economic situation has developed in the country. The change in the economic system was accompanied by a worsening of the country's political situation (loss of territories, civil war). It was from this time that people began to leave the country en masse in search of better living conditions.

Emigration flows were systematically increasing. The main reason was the difficult economic and social conditions. A significant problem has become the shortage of jobs. A significant part of the population abandoned the village, either moved to the city or went abroad to save themselves. Obviously, it was not only a form of mechanical movement of the population. This was followed by a number of serious changes in the country's gender and age structure, which was reflected in the worsening demographic situation: The share of the young generation in rural areas has significantly decreased, the number of elderly people has increased

every year, marriages have decreased, a significant declining of the birth rates has led to depopulation, and the population is experiencing demographic aging. Disruption of the gender-age structure is not just a numerical characteristic. It causes many social changes and complications in the country - mostly young and middle-aged people participate in migration processes, which is related to the so-called "brain drain" of educated, professional personnel and specialists from the country. The elderly population is not actively participating in the labor process, and at the same time, health-related problems are increasing, which requires offering and ensuring appropriate conditions for senior and elderly generation of the population (from the perspective of geriatrics and gerontology).

An equally important issue with elderly people is the use of their knowledge, skills, and experience. In European countries, they have been talking about the "silver economy" for years (sometimes also referred to as the "silver economy"...). The issue is on the agenda precisely at a time when most of the younger generation is involved in immigration processes and there are a number of professions, specialties, and workplaces where the elderly and demographically aging population can be boldly used due to their rich experience and work capacity.

The process that began in the last decade of the 20th century is still one of the most important and painful topics for the country. In fact, the growing rate of migration in Georgia clearly indicates that there are still insufficient jobs in the country that cannot fully meet the demand for the existing workforce.

According to official data from the National Statistics Office of Georgia, the share of the young gener-

ation (under 30 years old) in the total number of immigrants from Georgia is quite high. The outflow of young people from the country is a serious and quite important problem. Most of them rarely return to the country due to much better employment conditions (higher salaries). The emigration of the younger generation has increased significantly since visa liberalization (2014), a significant portion of young people are

students. On the basis of exchange programs, they go to study in higher education institutions of European countries, they "adapt" well to the European environment and in many cases they stay to study. Unfortunately, educated young people also choose European countries to work (table 1). (The decline in 2020-2022 was due to the Covid-19 pandemic).

Table 1.

Number and Share of Emigrated Georgian Citizens (under 30) Among Emigrants (2014-2024)

Year	Number of emigrants	Share of emigrants (%)
2014	31374	45
2016	29842	44
2018	32348	42
2020	15209	35
2022	39644	39
2023	114438	70
2024	150320	72

Source: National Statistical Office of Georgia

Obviously, the positive side of this event is important, because young people have the opportunity to receive modern and comprehensive knowledge and education. If possible, if they have the appropriate conditions to return to their home country (high salary, career advancement), they will use this knowledge for their own country.

In recent years, the number of children among the total number of migrants has increased significantly, due to the fact that they are now more often leaving the country with their families. This fact is quite thought-provoking and noteworthy. If this trend continues, the age structure of the Georgian population will experience significant negative changes.

Table 2.3.

Age Structure of Citizens Emigrated in 2023

Age	Number of people left the country	Specific share %
0-14	70003	43
15-29	44435	27
30-44	27846	17
45 +	21196	13

Source: National Statistical Office of Georgia

Despite the existing difficulties, the positive side of migration processes is immigrants' remittances. Due to a number of social and economic problems in the country, it is a source of livelihood for a significant portion of families remaining in Georgia. There is nothing to hide that these remittances are one of the sources of foreign exchange inflows for the country. It plays a fairly large role in terms of the country's economic stability.

In 2020, the EU-funded project "Long-Term Migration Strategy of Georgia for 2021-2030" was prepared as part of the broader EU-Georgia Visa Liberalization Action Plan, which "forms a country's long-term vision on the main directions of the migration field and at the same time places significant demands on implementation, mechanisms, and involved agencies".

The presented strategy, based on a review of the current situation and a description of sectoral aspects, includes a number of directions, such as: Improving migration management, promoting legal migration and combating illegal migration, reintegration of returned

emigrants, active involvement of the diaspora in the development of the country, development of the asylum system, integration of foreigners. An analysis of the current situation has been conducted on the individual components of the strategy, and goals and objectives have been prepared accordingly. It can be safely said that the full implementation of the objectives of the Migration Strategy of Georgia for 2021-2039 will significantly change and improve a significant part of the main problems related to Georgian immigrants.

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